

PERCEPTION OF THE YOUTH ON GENDER BIASES IN MODERN SOCIETY

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“Gender equality is the unfinished business of the 21st century”-Elizabeth Broderick

Gender equality has been an issue all over the world from ancient times. Since ages, women, in society, have not been treated at par with the males and gender inequality has been existing. Since the few years, there has been a great emphasis on treating all human being equal irrespective of their gender. We are in the 21st century and we are still talking, discussing and finding solution for gender discrimination, gender inequality etc. This is a worldwide subject that seems to get “better” as the years go by but unfortunately it doesn't seem to have an end. Our spiritual beliefs consider women as deities on one hand and yet society fails to identify her as a human being first on the other. The search of equality between genders is fuelling a never-ending war between women and men.

Gender bias exists in every aspect of society—from the workplace to the political arena. In modern society gender inequality is the unequal treatment of someone based off their gender rather than their varying skills, abilities, and characteristics. Abolishing all kinds of discrimination in our societies is a responsibility of everyone, regardless of gender, economic, political, or social status. Many efforts have been taken in the past to get rid of this unequal gap between genders.

Gender affects every aspect of our life, from how we feel about ourselves and set our goals in educational, recreational and work opportunities as well as the nature and extent of our participation in social and civic life. It has a strong impact on the way we practice our religion, the way we dress, the way we express our feelings and the nature of all of our relationships with others.

Gender bias can refer to slightly different beliefs or attitudes:

1. The credence that one gender or sex is lower to or more valued than the other which is either female or male chauvinism.
2. The attitude of hatred of females (misogyny) or hatred of males (misandry); as well as the attitude of imposing a partial and/or false notion of masculinity on males and femininity on females, or vice versa.
3. A feeling of distrust towards the opposite or same sex as a whole.

Even today, gender biases are still predominant in the society and is visible at home, workplace and community around. The researcher thus wants to find out the Perception of the Youth on Gender Biases in Modern Society.

Need and Importance of the study:

The present study will help to find out the Perception of the Youth on Gender Biases in Modern Society.

Statement of problem:**Perception of the Youth on Gender Biases in Modern Society****Aim of the study**

To find out the Perception of the Youth on Gender Biases in Modern Society and to analyze the rate of biasness at place of work, home and society.

Research Questions:

1. How does the youth perceive gender biases in modern society?
2. Are the women of today facing the same discrimination as compared to the women of earlier times?
3. To what extent does gender biases take place in work, home and society?

Objectives:

- To find out the how does the youth perceive gender biases in modern society.
- To understand if women of today's society are facing the same discrimination that the women of earlier times?
- To analyze the rate of gender biases that takes place at places such as work, home, society etc.

Research Methodology:

Descriptive Survey Method was used for the purpose of the research because the study intends to find how does the youth perceive gender biases in modern society.

Sampling:

In present research, researcher included 40 youth has been done through incidental sampling.

Tool and Techniques for Data Collection:

A rating scale was prepared by the researcher to find out the perception of the youth on Gender Biases in Modern Society. The percentage was analyzed.

Data Collection:

Data was collected from 40 youth.

ANALYSIS OF THE RESPONSE OF THE PERCEPTION OF THE YOUTH ON GENDER BIASES IN MODERN SOCIETY

Sr. No.	STATEMENTS	YES%	NO%
1.	Girls usually face religious restriction.	86%	14%
2.	Have you ever felt gender discrimination from the family on the basis of religion?	13%	87%
3.	Friends show gender discrimination on the basis of religion.	20%	80%
4.	Teachers usually show gender discrimination on the basis of your religion.	40%	60%
5.	Teachers are usually harsh with boys.	60%	40%
6.	Media depicts women like the are TABOO.	57%	43%
7.	Females athletes are usually denied opportunities in sports.	53%	47%
8.	Females are denied incentives.	33%	67%
9.	Selection criteria are usually in favour of males	58%	42%
10.	Majority of departments prefer a man's team	80%	20%

Findings & Discussion

As per the above survey conducted here are some of the findings to understand why people have these opinions.

- 1) On the basis of religion 86% believe that women do face religious restriction as these beliefs has been carried out for centuries and has been inculcated in family's for generations to come. The non-participation of women to participate in religious activities has been visible in the mediaeval times. This is how women have been taught to behave and act in today's modern society.
- 2) Though most women are of the opinion that girls face religious restrictions, 87% agree that they have not felt gender discrimination from the family on the basis of religion. 80% of the youth are of the opinion that their friends so not show gender discrimination on the basis of religion.

- 3) We also understand that gender biases do not only take place with girls but also boys where in the girls can impose false accusations towards him and he bears the consequences just because he's a man.
- 4) Talking about media it has become one of the largest modes of communication, having said that it has created a lot of controversies by portraying women as they are TABOO and over 57% believe that it is true.
- 5) Now on the basis of sports or work women of today are very talented and challenging but ignoring their talent today's society feels most women shouldn't take part in any kind of athletic events and should stay at home and take care of the family. Whereas in a work place women have proved to be more efficient in their work than men as they have better decision taking skills and a composed mind during stressful situations and hence females are great multitaskers.
- 6) As of in multinational companies where high profit deals or some kind of task where a man is in charge he will always prefer a man to be in his team because of how women are portrayed as and in today's society a man and women working together alone late night due to some important work creates a lot of controversies.

Conclusion:

The youth do feel that gender biases exist even today in modern society and they find it visible at home, workplace and the status of women in society. They are of the opinion that the women of today are still discriminated like the women of yester years although they find there are improvements in the legality of equal treatment given to both genders.

There has been growth in the area of equality and reduction of biases among genders with regards to equal rights to education with the introduction of Free and Compulsory education irrespective of caste, colour, creed, religion and gender. Yet in some parts of the country and the world around the girls and women are continuing to suffer from violence and discrimination. There is therefore a dire need to make our legal and regulatory framework stronger for fighting the deep- embedded practice of gender equality by offering gender equality in areas of health services, education, job and involvement in administrative and decision making. The whole world must recognize the efforts of men and women equally in modern society which is of utmost importance.

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